

Title: Engaging Global Virtual Teams: A theoretical framework proposal on employee engagement predictors in global virtual settings.

Abstract: In a globalized world, where technology, processes and information are more accessible than ever, the differential factor between success or failure is the human capital. Yet, if our workforce is not engaged we will not be able to obtain its full potential or simply the talent will flee to greener pastures. Another trait of the globalization is the increasing use of Global Virtual Teams (GVTs) to manage a great variety of projects and endeavours in our organizations across multiple cultures, but we are still failing to recognize their different needs and challenges. This paper aims to be a first step towards filling this gap and reviews the existing literature on GVTs in order to propose a framework of predictors of employee engagement, from which to set a model describing the drivers behind employee engagement in virtual and multicultural environments.

Key words: global virtual teams; virtual organizations; virtual teams; GVT; employee engagement; work engagement; predictor; job demands; job resources; information & communication technology; ICT; intercultural; social capital; trust; transformational leadership.

1. Introduction

We are living a revolution in our work environment where the pace of structural change is more pervasive, rapid, and global in its context: Globalization has melted national borders and the information & communications revolution has made geography and time irrelevant (Passaris, 2006). The physical barriers for accessing talented resources are removed thanks to technology and the use of global virtual teams. Companies don't need to limit their growth based on their local pool of knowledge, since virtuality allows them to hire or cooperate anywhere, faster and with lower costs than ever before. These virtual teams are seen by many consultants and researchers as the nuclei of 21st century organizations. (Harvey, Novicevic and Garrison, 2004).

Parallel to this revolution, a major concern over the low engagement levels of the workforce has been widely shared among private and public companies, even at government and national organization levels. Several studies show that the engagement gap is far from being filled (Cipd, 2006; Macleod and Clarke, 2009; Harter *et al.*, 2016). In this scenario where many companies fail to achieve an engaged workforce a reactive approach to low levels of engagement is generally very generic, and uses practices which treat all employees independently of their work characteristics with one-size-fits-all policies. The virtual revolution we are facing and the distinctive characteristics of global and remote work require, in our opinion, a more focused approach which should be different to the one in traditional work settings. Yes, there is an engagement deficit today, but the vertiginous speed at which the world is changing should make organizations focus on tomorrow's virtual workforce, a present future already in many industries, if they want to obtain the benefits of globalization and survive its challenges. Organizations must consider whether their leaders and workforce are sufficiently prepared to face these changes: in this globalized world, people is the differential factor. GVTs should not be different, therefore it

is of key importance for companies and leaders to understand what is driving the different behaviours and consequent performance results. The behaviour of people at work is what ultimately tilts the balance between operational success or failure (Macleod and Clarke, 2009). The obsolete idea of transactional relationships, and employee retention for only extrinsic rewards, especially in a virtual world where the competition to capture talent is global, will undoubtedly lead many companies to limit their growth, development or even affect their viability due to their inability to access or retain qualified resources.

To shed some light into the virtual resource management, in this paper we are proposing a theoretical framework considering the antecedents of engagement specific to GVTs. This will help leaders and organizations to identify the singular aspects of their work environment over which they should be able to influence and the intrinsic personal characteristics they should be searching for in candidates when staffing virtual teams. Both characteristics will be instrumental to increase the level of engagement of their members. We will underpin our proposal on the Job Demand-Resources theory, which allows us to shape any working environment or job characteristic by identifying the demands and resources that workers face in their daily job. When referring to GVTs, we have gone through a thorough review of the large literature available on the subject what has allowed us to identify and select a comprehensive group of constructs that exert influence on the engagement outcomes.

We consider this model relevant for GVT leaders who will benefit from identifying the key aspects to concentrate on in order to obtain high levels of performance from their teams as a consequence of engagement and identify the desirable skills when selecting the GVT members. We also aim to raise awareness to a strategic corporate level about the importance of deploying specific engagement policies for this particular profile of workforce, to grasp the full potential of

virtual employees as well as assuring their wellbeing. By the end of the paper, we will suggest future lines of research, including the empirical validation of our proposals.

2. GVTs are on the rise.

Along with internationalization and globalization many organizations have responded to the dynamic environment by introducing virtual teams that coordinate their work predominantly with electronic information and communication technologies (e-mail, video-conferencing, etc.) (Hertel, Geister and Konradt, 2005). GVTs are commonly assigned the most critical organizational tasks: development of new global products, cross-border mergers, acquisitions and alliances, coordinating global account management programs, key research and development projects, etc (Maznevski and Chudoba, 2000). Yet they will benefit from the best talents because work, knowledge generation, management, and innovation are no longer locally or geographically bound and can respond more easily to the changing requirements of the environment by making use of the latest knowledge, and adaptable working arrangements (Lilian, 2014). We need to go back 30 years in the academic literature to find the first definitions for GVTs as temporary, culturally diverse, geographically dispersed and electronically communicated work groups (Kristof et al. 1995, 229-253; Jarvenpaa and Leidner 1998). Three main pillars underpin this kind of teams:

2.1. Virtual Concept.

“Virtual” designates distributed works that are mainly based on electronic information and communication tools. (Hertel, Geister and Konradt, 2005) There is no clear definition of the balance between face-to-face and virtual interaction between team members, but in general it is believed that face-to-face interaction tends to be from non-existent to very uncommon in remote teams. However, it is customary to organize a face-to-face Kick-off Meeting in order to build an

atmosphere of trust even with the remote members located in different countries. (Daim *et al.*, 2012) As a consequence to virtuality, members separated across time and space are heavily reliant on technology that allows them to communicate and engage in collaborative activities. (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998) and they benefit from the rapid development of electronic means of communication and their reduction in cost in recent times, making distributed work much easier, faster and more efficient.

2.2. Global Concept.

As for the global concept, it implies both cultural diversity and geographic dispersion. Members can be separated not only physically, but also temporally due to their placement in different time zones and with different working hours and schedules, but nonetheless they can and should think and act considering the diversities found in this global environment. (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998) This temporal separation restricts not only the possibility of face to face but also synchronous communication. In highly geographically dispersed teams, it is more difficult to coordinate resources, given that there are shorter windows of time for synchronous meetings, and many meetings take place outside standard hours. (Gibson and Gibbs, 2006)

The concept of culture is broader than just the culture, native languages or value systems of the different nationalities (Dekker, Rutte and Van den Berg, 2008), and it is characterized by “the collective programming of the human mind that distinguishes the members of one human group from another” (Hofstede, 1993). Within the global teams, multi-functional and inter-organizational collaborations are included (Lee-Kelley and Sankey, 2008). We must assume that we will find diversity by education or by training (engineers of various specialties, lawyers, accountants, physicists, biologists, psychologists, etc.) but also characteristics and business

values that define each stakeholder (business units, suppliers, clients, external services providers, consultants, etc.) that contributes to staff the project.

2.3. Concept of Temporality and Dynamism.

In the definition used by some authors (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998; Lipmack and Stamps, 1998) , it is commonly accepted that team members have never worked together before and will not do it again in the future, or at least they have that perception. Consequently, the team members do not share a common history or future and this will have implications on the generation of trust and reciprocity. The dynamic structure is also linked to temporality which implies that the team itself will morph in size and composition, where a handful of core members would form the main body of the team with other members joining or leaving as needed after completing their contribution (Lee-Kelley, 2006). This allows members to often participate simultaneously in several part-time projects where the content of work is also changing. (Verburg, Bosch-Sijtsema and Vartiainen, 2013).

3. Employee engagement: a popular undefinition.

The main idea behind the practical application of an engagement policy is to unleash the potential of people at work and thus, obtain measurable benefits for both the individual and the organization. It is about maintaining and developing commitment, energy and the desire to do a good job; that feeling that everyone has ever experienced "the first day of work", to maximize the individual performance and by extension the organizational one (Macleod and Clarke, 2009). These two different motivations, the business oriented and the occupational health, do not have to be at odds as the well-being of employees and their happiness should be the priority of every successful company to satisfy customers and achieve the best results. In other words, happy staff

results in happy customers and lots of happy customer results in happy shareholders (Azoury, Daou and Sleiaty, 2013).

HR consulting firms offer advice to their clients on how to improve the engagement level of their workforce to ultimately reach high engagement values, (Macey and Schneider, 2008) better performance in their particular role (Salanova, Agut and Peiró, 2005; Schaufeli, Taris and Bakker, 2006; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007; Bakker and Rodríguez Muñoz, 2012) and by extension, organizational success linked to an improvement in their operating and financial results, such as total return for the shareholder (Saks, 2006; Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2009b). But the meaning of engagement is still ambiguous among both academic researchers and practitioners. The term is used at different times to refer to both psychological states, traits and behaviours, as well as their antecedents and even outcomes. (Macey and Schneider, 2008) It has a diverse nomological network of constructs, but at the same time it has been poorly demonstrated theoretically and empirically (Macey and Schneider, 2008; Christian, Garza and Slaughter, 2011).

The first reference of the concept goes back to 1990 (Kahn, 1990) and it was defined as “the simultaneous employment and expression of a person’s *preferred self* in task behaviours that promote connections to work and to others, personal presence (physical, cognitive, and emotional) and active, full performances”. However the academic world did not paid much attention until recently when engagement has surfaced with special interest in the areas of Positive Psychology and Occupational Health Psychology motivated by their interest in employee wellbeing (Bakker *et al.*, 2008). In this area, two related schools of thought consider work engagement a positive, work-related state of well-being or fulfilment (Bakker *et al.*, 2008). The first considers engagement as the direct opposite of the 3 Burnout dimensions characterized by energy, involvement, and efficacy (Maslach and Leiter, 2000), and the second considers work

engagement as an independent, distinct concept that is related negatively to burnout and defined as “a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigour, dedication, and absorption” (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002). Engaged employees work hard (vigour), are involved (dedicated), and feel happily engrossed (absorbed) in their work (Bakker *et al.*, 2008)

We consider the latter to be the most adequate for building our model, not just for its clarity of definition but also because the instrument most often used to measure engagement is the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002) or its shortened version of 9 items (Schaufeli, Bakker and Salanova, 2006). In this model the three dimensions of engagement are defined as: (1) Vigour: characterized by high levels of energy and mental resilience while working, the willingness to invest effort in one’s work, and persistence even in the face of difficulties; (2) Dedication: refers to being strongly involved in one’s work and experiencing a sense of significance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge; and (3) Absorption: characterized by being fully concentrated and deeply engrossed in one’s work, whereby time passes quickly and one has difficulties with detaching oneself from work. (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002; Schaufeli, Bakker and Salanova, 2006)

4. Job Demand–Resources (JD-R) Theory: tailoring the engagement model.

According to the JD-R theory, all working environments or job characteristics can be modelled using just two different categories, namely job demands and job resources (Bakker and Demerouti, 2014) and additionally personal resources (Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2007), thus constituting an overarching model that may be applied to various occupational settings, irrespective of the particular demands and resources involved. (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). The model has been used to predict job burnout (Bakker, Demerouti and Verbeke, 2004), and work engagement (Bakker *et al.*, 2007), as well as consequences of these experiences, for

example: employee wellbeing (Salanova *et al.*, 2013), sickness absenteeism (Schaufeli, Bakker and van Rhenen, 2009) or job performance (Bakker, Demerouti and Verbeke, 2004).

Job demands refer to those physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of the job that require sustained physical and/or psychological effort and are therefore associated with certain physiological and/or psychological costs (Demerouti *et al.*, 2001). Job resources refer to those physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of the job that are: (a) functional in achieving work goals; (b) reduce job demands and the associated physiological and psychological costs; or (c) stimulate personal growth, learning, and development (Demerouti *et al.*, 2001). Personal resources are positive self-evaluations that are linked to resiliency and refer to individuals' sense of their ability to control and impact upon their environment successfully (Hobfoll *et al.*, 2003; Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2007)

JD-R theory proposes that job demands and resources are the triggers of two different psychological processes. (1) A health impairment process: job demands are generally the most important predictors of such outcomes as exhaustion and psychosomatic health complaints, (Bakker *et al.*, 2003; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007) because they require sustained effort and may exhaust employees' resources and lead to energy depletion (Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2007). (2) A motivational process: job resources are generally the most important predictors of work enjoyment, motivation, engagement (Bakker *et al.*, 2007; Bakker and Demerouti, 2014) and organizational commitment (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004). Finally, It has been argued and shown that positive self-evaluations of personal resources predict goal-setting, motivation, performance, job and life satisfaction (Judge, Van Vianen and De Pater, 2004), and they are functional in achieving goals, protect from threats and the associated physiological and psychological costs, and stimulate personal growth and development (Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2009a). In summary

employees who have many job and personal resources available can cope better with their daily job demands (Bakker and Demerouti, 2014).

5. Potential constructs for a model of antecedents.

The following sections explain our proposal of variables based in the GVT literature to characterize the main factors affecting employee engagement under the JD-R framework. Our aim in this section is to build a customized proposal valid for GVT work environments, which will be the base for future empirical studies to validate a final model.

5.1. Job Demands in GVTs

In order to identify job demands in GVTs we concentrated on the hindrances, challenges and difficulties, that affect both members and leaders in GVTs. These are provoked by the working conditions in such type of teams as particular cultural differences, distributed locations and tasks developed asynchronously, all through the use of technology. Additionally, we focused on burnout related topics such as strain, stress, health impairment, etc. For simplifications purposes, constructs that are not exclusive to GVTs but also present in traditional teams were not included, unless their significance in a virtual setting was clearly more predominant. These constructs have been arranged into four main groups, listed as: Intercultural communication, Team Politics, Affective conflict and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Demands.

5.1.1. Intercultural Communication.

In GVT environments it is common to have different national cultures and different native languages among the team members so Intercultural communication challenges are expected. The different culture and mother tongue, and different proficiency level of the working language generate a lack of accuracy in both written and spoken language, requiring team members to invest more time and effort in encoding and decoding messages (Shachaf, 2008). Even when

mastering the vocabulary and grammar of the foreign language, sometimes the literal meaning will not allow members to capture aspects about the social context and subtleties or possible reinterpretations. (Wlotko and Federmeier, 2013)

The communication style is also related to culture (Hall, 1976). Low-context (LC) communication, characteristic of individualistic cultures, involves the use of explicit and direct messages in which meanings are contained mainly in the transmitted messages. In opposition, High-context (HC) communication, predominantly in collectivistic cultures, involves the use of implicit and indirect messages in which meanings are embedded in the person or in the sociocultural context. (Gudykunst *et al.*, 1996) When low and high-context member cohabit in a team, and there is lack of awareness of the opposite culture it can generate frustration and misunderstandings. (Todd, 2013).

Another remark about cultural communication, or more precisely the lack of it, is the “mum” effect. Mum, with the intended meaning of keeping silent, is defined as the reluctance or failure to deliver negative information or undesirable messages. (Rosen and Tesser, 1970). Culture is perceived as a potential factor for the mum effect (Ramingwong and Snansieng, 2013) and has been reviewed using Hofstede’s work (Hofstede, 1993) concluding that Power distance, individualism and long-term orientation contribute to the mum effect. (Sajeev and Ramingwong, 2010; Todd, 2013).

5.1.2. Team politics.

Organizational politics refers to the complex mixture of power, influence and short-term or long-term self-interest seeking behaviours that dominate an individual’s activity in the workplace which may or may not be at the expense of other members’ interests (Ferris *et al.*, 1989; Vigoda,

2002) with potential for dysfunctional outcomes at both the individual and the team level (Gilmore *et al.*, 1996) for example increased competition with others, decreased cooperation with others (Baruch and Lin, 2012), loss of strategic power and position credibility, negative feeling towards others, internal feeling of guilt and hampered job performance leading to job distress and job burnout (Vigoda, 2002). In the case of the GVTs, where different business units, functions and national and organizational cultural differences and affinities cohabit within the team, we may expect organizational politics to be more present than in a collocated team.

5.1.3. Affective conflict.

Affective conflict is characterized by person-related disagreements that include “tension, animosity, and annoyance among the team members” (Jehn, 1995) and arises because of personality clashes and continued cognitive disagreements that may trigger animosity among the members (Janssen, Van De Vliert and Veenstra, 1999; Parayitam and Dooley, 2009). In GVTs, technology and the lack of opportunity for face-to-face cues while interacting are major sources of conflict (Ayoko, Konrad and Boyle, 2012) both cognitive and affective . Also the difficulty identifying the existence of these conflicts due to the lack of non-verbal communication clues causes them to be prolonged over time, potentially transforming into affective conflicts. (Karen A Jehn, 1997)

5.1.4. ICT Demands

ICT is defined as any electronic device or technology that has the ability to gather, store, process or send information. (Steinmueller, 2000). Technology is at the core of GVTs because without internet, email, video and audio conferences, virtual drives, mobile devices, etc. teams can't even exist. (Daim *et al.*, 2012) For this reason we must consider the specific aspects of ICT which are associated with increased strain, stress, and burnout. They vary from Immediate response

expectations and permanent availability to suffering from ineffective communication, hassles with the technology and their continuous upgrade, and in some cases an increased workload despite the improved efficiency that technology provides (Day *et al.*, 2012).

5.2. Job Resources for GVTs

In a similar way, we are proposing a compilation of job resources obtained through a thorough review of the literature and specifically of contributions of concepts such as performance, effectiveness, success factors, knowledge sharing and motivational aspects, assuring a perfect fit with the definition of job resources. We have grouped them into 3 main categories: Adequate media richness, Social Capital which includes Trust, Shared vision and Social Interaction, and Transformational Leadership.

5.2.1. Adequate media richness

Rich Media Theory (RMT) sustains that Organizational success is based on the organization's ability to process information of appropriate richness in order to reduce uncertainty (absence of information) and clarify equivocality (ambiguity of the information) (Daft and Lengel, 1986). In other words, greater quantity of information can reduce uncertainty whereas better quality of information can decrease equivocality (Lin, Standing and Liu, 2008). It is subject to media's ability for instant feedback; the capacity to include cues as body language, voice, tone; ability to establish a personal focus; and variety of language, differing from natural. (Daft and Lengel, 1986).

According to the RMT, rich media will lead to better performance, (Daft and Lengel, 1986) in particular for intangible knowledge sharing or equivocal tasks like highly complex organizational issues, company strategy, objectives or goals.

However, there is some controversy whether that is always the case. In GVTs we may find other aspects not considered in the RMT. Huge differences in culture and language may play a determinant role in the effectiveness of the media chosen. According to Klitmøller and Luring (2013) in teams with great cultural differences among their members, rich media could provide an unnecessary excess of cultural cues hampering understanding, so lean media will be more effective for sharing simple knowledge. Also, when language differences are significant, leaner media (i.e. e-mails) erases verbal misunderstandings thereby it raises the certainty level making the knowledge-sharing process more effective.

Choosing the adequate media for each task or message sometimes may not be in the hands of all members or team managers, as certain processes may be predefined or simply not all available in the organizations. GVTs are limited in the use of rich media like face to face, or even synchronic communication (phone, videocalls) when members are located in different time zones.

(Workman, Kahnweiler and Bommer, 2003) It is an important resource to reduce communication breakdown, misunderstanding and in consequence conflicts among team members. Other aspects to be considered when choosing media in GVTs is that computer-based communication media may eliminate the type of communication cues that individuals use to convey trust, warmth, attentiveness, and other interpersonal affections. (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998)

5.2.2. Social Capital

It is the set of informal values or norms shared among members of a group that permit cooperation among them (Fukuyama, 1997) and where we can distinguish three dimensions (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 2011). (1) The structural dimension is the configuration of the physical ties that connect members and make access to resources possible, in our case we identified it as

Social Interaction. (2) The relational dimension which is the emotional and affective status within the social network which facilitates the exchange of resources between members (Hsu and Hung, 2013), for us, trust. Finally, the (3) Cognitive dimension referring to those resources providing shared representations, interpretations, and systems of meaning among parties, which allow members to effectively access resources. (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 2011; Hsu and Hung, 2013), that we define as Shared Vision.

Social interaction is the way team members talk to and act with each other in a team. Previous research indicates that social interaction among team members boosts voluntary and personal modes of cooperation and restrains deliberate competition (Baruch and Lin, 2012), promotes shared knowledge with each other and access to specific resources (Tsai, 2002) and even leads to radical innovation (Daim *et al.*, 2012). It is clearly functional in achieving team objectives and expected to reduce the costs associated with team politics and personal conflicts. GVTs' challenge is finding the opportunity to interact socially.

Trust is a positive attitude held by a team member towards another member. It is built on the assumption that the latter will act by fair-play rules and will not take advantage of one's state of vulnerability and dependence in a risky situation (Mansor, Mirahsani and Saidi, 2012) so it allows them to engage in risk-associated activities that they cannot control or monitor (Daim *et al.*, 2012). Possibly, it is one of the most studied topics within the success factors in teams and in particular for GVTs as one of the major reasons for failure is related to building trust (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998). In GVTs members may never actually meet in person, they must function without face-to-face contact and visual cues (Ridings, Gefen and Arinze, 2002) and cannot develop trust in the traditional way because they lack of common social norms, frequent social interactions, shared experiences or anticipation of future association (Daim *et al.*, 2012).

A shared vision is intended to generate a clear organizational purpose and direction as to what to preserve and what to change in the organization so that it can achieve its desired future outcomes. (Loon Hoe, 2007). It helps reduce ambiguity, uncertainty, conflict, irritation and communication misunderstanding, and consequently facilitates emotion-sharing processes and positive social interactions among team members. (Baruch and Lin, 2012) In the case of GVTs, where members may belong to different business units, companies, functions, etc. it is even more important to have a clearly defined, communicated and accepted vision among the team members, since the different organizations cohabiting in the GVTs may have unintentionally conflicting interests and business objectives that may cloud that very same team vision.

5.2.3. Transformational Leadership

Proposed for the first time by James MacGregor Burns (Burns, 1978), transformational leadership is characterized by idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration (Bass and Avolio, 1994). Transformational leaders focus on high-level needs, such as esteem, competence, self-fulfilment and the full development of one's potential (Johnson, 2015). Previous studies on leadership particularized to the case of virtual teams suggest that transformational leadership is more useful in situations where there are greater difficulties in coordinating tasks and building relationships (Purvanova and Bono, 2009). In particular when media richness is lacking, the facilitation offered by a transformational leader is helpful for building a cooperative climate which helps to focus on the task as a group and not as individuals and thus achieve the accomplishment of tasks improving the productivity of the team (Huang, Kahai and Jestice, 2010). Another important aspect that transformational leaders develop are social relationships with team members (Joshi, Lazarova and Liao, 2009), which in virtual environments is hampered by geographical, temporal and cultural distance.

5.3. Personal resources of GVTs' members.

In order to particularize Personal resources in the case of GVTs, for our model, we have referred to the different theories on competencies for virtual teamwork (Hertel, Geister and Konradt, 2005; Hertel, Konradt and Voss, 2006; Krumm and Hertel, 2012) and selected those aspects that fall under the definition of personal resources. These competencies, very often referred as Knowledge, Skills, Abilities and Other characteristics (KSAOs), are grouped differently depending on the author. We have opted for the following categorization that will facilitate the alignment with the described job demands and resources from previous sections: Teamwork KSAs, self-management skills, disposition to trust, technical proficiency and intercultural skills.

5.3.1. Teamwork KSAs

Teamwork competencies are related to social and interpersonal aspects that we identify as cooperativeness, conflict management and communication skills. In the virtual setting the reduced personal interaction and lack of common context increases the risk of misunderstandings, conflicts and neglect feelings and cooperativeness. (Hertel, Konradt and Voss, 2006) The importance of communication skills is less obvious in virtual teams because face-to-face interaction is generally reduced and therefore verbal skills are less relevant. However, communication skills should be understood as a wide spectrum of virtual setting possibilities from face-to-face situations, which are mostly limited, to asynchronous computer-mediated communications, more typically (Berry, 2011). The latter oblige team members to invest more time and effort to communicate effectively (Krumm and Hertel, 2012).

5.3.2. Self-management skills

GVTs context makes direct supervision unfeasible and other factors contributing to social control like geographical proximity, similar background and experience are mostly absent (Jarvenpaa,

Knoll and Leidner, 1998). Consequently, self-management skills are particularly important and should include four major aspects: independence, persistence, learning motivation, and creativity. (Hertel, Konradt and Voss, 2006) Independence, as the ability to plan and organize one's own activities without external support, is related to self-efficacy beliefs and thereby removes dysfunctional fears (Bandura, 1977). Persistence includes aspects of self-motivation, endurance of goal striving, and continuing activities after interruptions which are common in virtual communication (e.g. email and phone calls) (Bakker and Rodríguez Muñoz, 2012). Creativity and learning motivation, which include the intrinsic interest in new and unknown contents, are relevant for adapting frequently to a technological and organizational changing environment.

5.3.3. Disposition to trust

It refers to the willingness to depend on others with the belief that better results will be obtained by trusting them regardless of whether this trust is justified. (McKnight, Cummings and Chervany, 1998). In virtual settings with a finite life span, trust cannot be built gradually and time pressure hinders the ability of team members to develop expectations of others based on first-hand information (Jarvenpaa and Leidner, 1998), so members import expectations of trust from other settings with which they are familiar (Meyerson, Weick and Kramer, 1996). In such situations, we believe that disposition to trust will have a significant effect on initial trust among team members.

5.3.4. Technical proficiency

Team members' confidence in their ability to effectively learn and use new technologies is critical to their adoption propensity (Ratchford and Barnhart, 2012). This leads us to think that members with high values of technical proficiency will accept technology to a greater degree

mitigating the effects of the demands associated with technology and facilitating the interaction and communication with the other members of the virtual teams.

5.3.5. Intercultural skills

Following the broader meaning of culture under the Global aspect of GVTs discussed previously, the sensitivity and handling of such heterogeneity and cultural differences is an important resource for working in a virtual team. (Hertel, Konradt and Voss, 2006) These skills will enable team members to collaborate, address conflict, sustain intra-team relations and create an effective knowledge-sharing culture. (Zakaria, Amelinckx and Wilemon, 2004).

Figure 1. Graphical conceptual representation of the proposed elements of the JD-R balance for GVTs.

6. Discussion

6.1. Theoretical Implications

This paper introduces a simplified conceptual model that represents the equilibrium of forces existing between job demands and both job & personal resources in GVTs. Several models in the occupational health literature propose that job strain is the result of a disturbance in the existing equilibrium between the demands employees are exposed to and the resources they have at their disposal (Bakker and Demerouti, 2014). Through the comprehension and the monitorization of the elements at both sides of the balance, we gain a powerful tool to overcome the strain experienced by members of GVTs, fostering their engagement and excelling their performance.

The addition of personal resources into the model also contributes to explain the importance of the right selection of GVTs members. Is everyone equally prepared to cope with the demands that global and virtual environments require today? According to the model, the personal resources will provide GVTs' members with means to overcome demanding conditions and to prevent from negative outcomes and contribute to predict work engagement. (Xanthopoulou *et al.*, 2007). We have found theoretical evidence of how the pieces of this puzzle contributes to the creation of engagement, and confirm in which side of the balance they should belong to. However, we but cannot confirm the relative size of each piece, yet. This is to say, their level of significance or how much they contribute to tilt the scale to the engagement side or to the other.

6.2. Implications for organizations and leaders of GVTs.

As for the practical contribution, by studying this model, team leaders may increase their knowledge about the challenges that GVTs' members, including themselves, face in contrast to teams based in traditional settings. Anticipating undesired outcomes will lead to vastly engaged team members who will identify themselves with the success of the organization and win fulfilment from their contributions (Andrew and Sofian, 2012).

So how could the team leader influence the engagement outcomes based on the model we propose? By intervening earlier once they understand the particularities of the team and the work settings. Not all GVTs find themselves under the same level of Job Demands pressure. The composition of the team will define the level of cultural homogeneity or diversity and this will have direct impact on communication due to the different language levels and communication styles, requiring sustained effort and being a possible cause of misunderstandings. Cultural distance index and proficiency in the working language alone may not fully capture the complexities of intercultural communication (Froese, Peltokorpi and Ko, 2012) so for the

manager it will not be easy to predict just from these inputs. However, to mitigate the effect on the strain process caused by these job demands, they can make available range of different communication tools and technology solutions with proper training so the team can correctly select the right media to improve the communication effectiveness (Klitmøller and Lauring, 2013). The recruiting and selection of members with sufficient communications, technology competence and intercultural skills will prevent the appearance of “cultural noise” that could undermine the communication process among the members of the team.

The team leaders will need to consider scheduling periodic face-to-face meetings in order to understand the challenges that team members might be facing, as well as to enable the creation of interpersonal relationships between the team members, including the leader himself or herself, and the building of social capital and trust. (Lee-Kelley and Sankey, 2008). These outcomes are functional to prevent affective conflicts from happening, which are perceived as difficult to resolve and containing much negative emotion difficult to eliminate. Although this approach will bring costs to the organization, it is necessary to consider the existing hidden costs that underlie in not fostering, to some extent, the face to face contact among GVTs members, in particular during the initial phases of the team creation. Once the team is gaining maturity and performs according to the expectations, trust based on performance compensates for lack of social interaction (Kirkman *et al.*, 2002) Nevertheless, special vigilant attitude is needed in GVTs as non-resolved emotional conflicts are not easy to identify and when managers are not able to stop the escalation of conflict and resolve it, it has the potential for disaster (Karen A. Jehn, 1997). In all cases, trust is key to mitigate many relational demands but in virtual teams it needs to be formed quickly.

However, the challenge of building trust in cross-cultural settings falls under two behavioural categories. The first one is credibility. This is when one of the parties believes that the other party has the capabilities, competence, expertise and resources to make a successful exchange between them to meet the outcome expectations and will act in a reliable and predictable manner to meet them (Zakaria, Amelinckx and Wilemon, 2004). The leaders should use the earliest opportunity to foster this credibility and assure that the members of the team do not have different expectations on the functioning of the GVT caused by the cultural differences, especially when the member's intercultural skills are missing or are not very solid. The second would be benevolence understood as the beliefs about the emotional aspects of the other's behaviour like a positive intention to exchange, good will and that it will not jeopardize but enhance the outcomes through the interaction of the members of the team (Zakaria, Amelinckx and Wilemon, 2004). Only the *Disposition to trust* will facilitate the generation of these beliefs, making it a good skill to develop when working in this setting facilitating job and life satisfaction, (Judge, Van Vianen and De Pater, 2004) and protecting from threats (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2009a) derived from relational demands like team politics, affective conflict or misunderstandings derived from intercultural communications.

Organizational politics is another source of conflict in the work environment which, as we mentioned before, is linked to decreased cooperation with others (Baruch and Lin, 2012). The identification of this demand in the workgroup, whether is caused by individual traits, cultural backgrounds or different conflict of interest of the organizational units or functions that staff the team, should clearly encourage the leaders to reinforce the shared vision of the team. This will create a sense of commonality within the organization and provide coherence to the team activities, making them connected and bound together by a common aspiration (Loon Hoe,

2007). By doing so, the effects of this specific demand will be prevented or mitigated, including its associated physiological costs.

Organizations should promote transformational leadership practices, not just by identifying the natural transformational leaders and but also by training the more traditional leaders so they can grasp all the benefits identified previously in this paper. GVTs will benefit from this leadership style matching team members with the right self-management skills of independence, persistence, learning motivation, and creativity. All this should be analysed and weighed together with the technical skills or “in-role” related abilities (Hertel, Konradt and Voss, 2006), which are undoubtedly needed, but more often than not, soft skills seem to be relegated to a secondary selection criteria for virtual team members. The expertise in a certain technical subject will not protect the employee from the demands of global virtual settings and with lacking from the right soft skills will make members of GVTs be more exposed to strain and far from being engaged in their role.

To finalize, the unavoidable technology presence in the virtual world, and also increasingly in our societies, brings many benefits but may impact employee’s well-being (Day *et al.*, 2012). Some of the demands related to technology can be limited by company policies (response expectation, permanent availability) or a proactive involvement of the team members in the technology changes and implementation decision (control over technology) (Day *et al.*, 2012). At the same time, recruiting members that lack of a minimum confidence in their ability to effectively learn and use new technologies will make them be more exposed to these ICT demands and potentially to fall under increased strain, stress, and ultimately burnout.

6.3. Limitations and future research directions.

Our theoretical framework model is intended to include the most relevant aspects that potentially should contribute or hamper engagement in GVTs members based on the available literature. We could not find empirical evidence or studies that correlate all the constructs proposed in this paper directly with engagement values, but in its place, we could find correlations to known outcomes of engagement or burnout. Consequently, an empirical validation of the framework is necessary. We cannot dismiss the possibility that other constructs could predict engagement or that theoretical evidence of them being a potential antecedent may exist.

Another limitation is the endless arrangement of GVTs and its members' heterogeneity that may find combinations of cultures, environments, industries, activities or any other particularities that our generic approach to the broad definition of GVTs may not characterise them perfectly. We cannot discard a biased approach as a consequence of our own experience in the field.

Our first proposal for validating the model would include a cross-sectional study to analyse the significance of the different variables obtained directly from GVTs members' self-evaluations. In fact, a separate analysis for each facet of engagement would be required, as we should not expect the same level of significance of the antecedents for all the 3 facets. Being so, the model should be reduced, including only the most significant constructs in order to facilitate organizational leaders' decisions concerning where to concentrate efforts depending on their organizational context, so as to maximize the return of their actions towards a more engaged workforce. Once the first evaluation is concluded, there are multiple possibilities for further specific analysis over individual aspects of the model or to better identify and understand the influences between antecedents.

7. Conclusion.

This paper contributes to the virtual teams' management literature and provides a well-founded first step towards the construction a comprehensive model of antecedents of employee engagement particularized in GVTs. In this paper, we have proposed a theoretical framework that proves helpful for managers of GVTs and for organizations that their present or future are unavoidably virtual and/or global. It can also be used by researchers to run empirical studies on the topic.

Finally, we hope to increase the awareness of the importance of the idea of engagement so organizations can envision a safe and meaningful workplace without excessive amounts of stress and emotional exhaustion (May, Gilson and Harter, 2004) which would prevent individuals from working hard, being involved and feel happily engrossed (Bakker *et al.*, 2008), and where they might ultimately sacrifice their well-being. GVTs are the workforce of the future and being able to identify the key differences that engage their members rather than considering "one size fits all" will be the key to success in meeting the challenges of the globalized world and the new generations of employees' demands.

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Figure 1.

